

Field reaction of upland rice lines to root-knot nematode infestation at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station, Narathiwat, Thailand.

Cross	Selection no.	Infestation ^a (%)	Reaction ^b
SPR72103-67-2/IR208-78	SPRLR77205-3-2-1-4	37	MR
SPT7220-13-13-1/RD5	BKNLR77003-PSL-65021	81	S
RD11/IR28	SPRLR5010-149-1-1	92	S
RD1/IR28	SSPRLR75001-60-1-2	81	S
RD7/IET2845/IR4215-4-3-1-1	SPRLR223-53-2-2	87	S
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-5-08	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-6-030	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	44	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-15-050	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-17-091	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	25	R

^a Av of 4 replications. ^b R = 0-25% root galls, MR = 26-50%, MS = 51-75%, and S = 76-100%.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Soil and Crop Management

Organic matter as a P source for azolla

H. P. Barthakur and H. Talukdar, Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat 785013, Assam, India

Azolla culture with lowland rice is drawing farmer interest in northeastern India. P is essential for rapid azolla growth, and P deficiency gives azolla a red-brown color. For best azolla growth, 8.8 kg P/ha must be applied, which is more than the total fertilizer applied by farmers in Assam. We studied organic matter supplements to provide P for azolla.

Cow dung and poultry litter, applied to equal 9 kg P/ha at 1- or 2-mo intervals were compared to 0 and 9 kg P applied at 1-mo intervals.

Results (see table) showed that azolla growth increased from Mar to May, then declined from Jun to Aug. In May, the interaction of application intervals and organic matter sources was significant. Azolla grew better with 2-mo applications of cow dung and poultry litter.

Results indicated that when organic matter is used as a P source it should be applied well ahead of azolla inoculation so soil microorganisms can break it down and make it available as an azolla nutrient. Applying 9 kg P/ha as single superphosphate significantly increased azolla production. □

Azolla biomass production as affected by P application and 2 application intervals of cow dung and poultry litter, Assam, India.

Organic matter source	Application intervals (mo)	P as SSP ^a (kg/ha)	Azolla biomass production (t/ha)							
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
No organic matter	—	—	6.0	6.7	15.5	21.2	23.7	14.9	14.4	13.2
No organic matter	—	9	7.6	8.5	19.5	28.0	33.5	18.0	17.5	17.3
Cow dung	1	—	6.0	7.5	17.6	27.1	28.5	16.9	15.0	17.5
Cow dung	1	9	6.9	8.4	22.7	29.2	31.0	21.7	17.2	19.7
Poultry litter	1	—	5.6	8.1	16.6	23.7	24.0	18.4	17.2	20.7
Poultry litter	1	9	6.5	7.2	21.2	28.2	25.7	19.9	17.9	19.9
No organic matter	—	—	6.2	7.2	15.9	20.9	23.0	16.8	16.7	15.5
No organic matter	—	9	7.4	7.2	20.9	29.5	28.2	19.0	17.0	15.7
Cow dung	2	—	5.7	6.1	18.6	23.7	32.5	16.9	15.7	14.9
Cow dung	2	9	5.1	9.5	23.3	32.1	36.2	20.8	19.8	18.9
Poultrylitter	2	—	4.7	8.2	16.6	27.6	29.0	17.9	14.2	14.2
Poultrylitter	2	9	7.0	8.7	22.1	30.1	39.5	20.8	19.1	17.4
Mean	—	—	6.2	7.8	19.2	26.8	29.2	18.5	16.8	17.1
		SEm (P)	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.8
		CD (0.05)	0.8	ns	2.1	2.5	4.4	2.1	1.6	ns
		SEm (F × C)	0.4	0.6	1.3	1.5	2.6	1.3	1.0	1.5
		CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	7.7	ns	ns	ns

^a Single super phosphate.

Nitrogen requirement and spacing for late-transplanted, photoperiod-sensitive, tall indica rice

B. K. Singh, R. B. Thakur, and R. P. Singh, Agronomy Department, Rajendra Agricultural University (RAU), Pusa 848125, Bihar, India

In parts of Bihar, early Jul floods wash out lowland rice. Farmers retransplant in Aug with old seedlings of tall,

photoperiod-sensitive indicas. Sometimes, labor shortages also delay transplanting. We sought to identify a suitable rate and time of N application and spacing for Janaki, a new photoperiod-sensitive variety suitable for poorly drained lowlands. A field trial was conducted at RAU Research Farm in 1981 kharif.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Janaki was planted in four spacings and with six times and rates of N application (see

table). Spacings were in the main plot and N treatments in subplots. The soil was a silt loam with pH 8.5, 0.23% organic carbon, 17 kg available P/ha, 86 kg available K/ha, and EC 0.44 mmho/cm at 25°C.

Sixty-day-old Janaki seedlings were transplanted 8 Aug 1981. N was applied as urea. PK at 8.6 and 8.3 kg/ha as a single superphosphate and muriate of potash were applied at puddling. The crop was harvested 7 Dec 1981 from a net plot size of 6.25 m² and grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture.

N rate and timing significantly affected grain yield (see table). Maximum grain yield was obtained with 40 kg N/ha applied basally. It was 11 and 9% higher than yield with the same N applied in equal splits at transplanting and panicle initiation, or at transplanting and tillering. Higher yield was due mainly to more panicles/m².

At 20 kg N/ha, basal N application increased yield 10% over the same dose applied at panicle initiation. Poor yield

Grain yield and yieldcontributing characters as affected by different spacing and fertilizer treatments, Pusa, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)
Spacing (cm)				
20 × 20	1.7	119	18	2.5
20 × 15	1.9	149	18	2.2
15 × 15	1.9	171	18	2.1
20 × 10	2.0	177	17	2.0
Time and rate (kg/ha) of N application				
Control	1.6	143	18	2.0
20 as basal	1.9	159	18	2.4
20 at panicle initiation (PI)	1.7	149	17	2.1
40 as basal	2.2	171	18	2.3
20 as basal + 20 at PI	2.0	157	17	2.2
20 as basal + 20 at tillering	2.0	145	18	2.6
CD 5% for				
Spacing	ns	20	ns	0.2
Rate and time of N application	0.2	16	0.7	0.2

due to late N application may be associated with lower tiller productivity. These results indicate that time of N application was most critical for the late-transplanted crop.

Although the grain yield was statistically similar at different spacings,

20- × 15-cm spacing appeared to be best, and increased yield 12% over that with 20- × 20-cm spacing. Panicles/m² increased with closer spacing, while panicle weight and percent spikelet fertility decreased. Panicle length and 1,000-grain weight were unaffected by spacing. □

Effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla on rice

P. P. Joy and G. V. Havanagi, Agronomy Department, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore 560024, India

We studied the effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla (*Azolla pinnata* R. Br.) on rice in 1983 kharif. Soil was a sandy clay with pH 6.7, 285.50 kg available N/ha, 26.92 kg available P/ha, and 340.90 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with nine main plot and three subplot treatments in three replications. Main plot treatments were 0, 50, and 100 kg N/ha as urea and 0, 11, and 22 kg P/ha as single superphosphate. Subplot treatments were no azolla and azolla intercropped or dual-cropped with rice.

In the intercropped plots, 3t azolla/ha was inoculated 1 d after transplanting (DT) rice, grew with rice, and was incorporated twice after transplanting. In dual-cropped plots, 3 t azolla/ha was inoculated at 20 d before transplanting, allowed to grow as a monocrop and an

Table 1. Effect of different levels of N, P, and azolla on yield and yield parameters of rice, Bangalore, India, 1983 kharif.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain to straw ratio	Weight of single panicle (g)	Grain weight per panicle (g)
N (kg/ha)					
0	5.3	5.5	1.0	1.7	1.4
50	5.0	6.7	0.8	1.6	1.3
100	4.7	7.5	0.7	1.5	1.2
CD P: 0.05	ns	0.6	0.1	ns	ns
P (kg/ha)					
0	5.0	6.6	0.8	1.6	1.3
11	5.0	6.4	0.8	1.5	1.3
22	5.0	6.8	0.8	1.6	1.3
CD P: 0.05	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
No azolla					
Intercrop	5.1	5.8	0.9	1.7	1.4
Dual crop	5.2	6.3	0.9	1.7	1.4
	4.7	7.6	0.6	1.3	1.0
CD P: 0.05	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1
CD P: 0.01	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.2

^a ns = not significant.

intercrop, and incorporated twice each, before and after transplanting. N was applied in equal splits at transplanting and 30 DT, P was applied basally, and 42 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied basally to all plots. Jaya was transplanted

at 20- × 10-cm spacing on 18 Jul and harvested 19 Nov 1983.

Applying N and azolla improved rice growth and increased straw yield (Table 1). Grain yield was adversely affected at higher N levels and in dual azolla